

Search for Proton Decay: The Latest Results from Super-Kamiokande

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Abstract

An experimental observation of proton decay would become a unique evidence of the Grand Unified Theory. In this paper, the latest proton decay search results from Super-Kamiokande are described with emphasis on $p \rightarrow e^+ \pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+ \pi^0$ decay modes with Super-Kamiokande enlarged fiducial mass data from April 1996 to May 2018.

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1 Introduction

The standard model of elementary particle physics is based on the $SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y$ gauge symmetry for the strong interaction and the electroweak interaction. It has succeeded in predicting almost all experimental results however, it still leaves open questions about the universe, such as dark matter candidate, baryon asymmetry and so on. The Grand Unified Theory (GUT) [1] is proposed based on the electric charge quantization between quarks and leptons, and the running coupling constant unification among the electromagnetic, weak and strong interactions in the super high energy scale ($\sim 10^{16}$ GeV). Proton decay is a direct transition between quarks and leptons, and a common prediction among almost all GUT models. Since reaching the GUT energy scale with an accelerator is not a realistic, search for proton decay is a unique way to prove it. No significant proton decay candidates have been found so far and the Super-Kamiokande experiment is a world leading experiment about proton decay search. Hydrogen nucleus in water is suitable for the proton decay search because it is free from Fermi motion and various nuclear effects, such as final state interaction with other nuclei. We have performed searches for proton decay via $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ decay modes using the Super-Kamiokande data until May 2018. As an analysis improvement we have enlarged the Super-Kamiokande detector fiducial mass region from 22.5 kton to 27.2 kton. In this paper, the results from this analysis are described first and other decay mode search results using the conventional fiducial mass are described later.

2 The Super-Kamiokande Detector

Super-Kamiokande is a cylindrical 50-kiloton water Cherenkov ring imaging detector, located in the Mozumi mine of Gifu prefecture, Japan. Its height and diameter are about 40 m each. The detector contains two optically separated regions, an inner detector (ID) and an outer detector (OD). More than 11000 (40 % photo coverage) 50-cm photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) facing inwards collect Cherenkov light emitted from charged particles in the ID, while 1885 20-cm PMTs facing outwards work as a veto detector for cosmic-ray muons and their Michel electrons. Detailed descriptions of the detector and its calibration can be found in [2, 3].

The SK data taking period used for this work is summarized in Table 1. Each detector configuration is different phase by phase. SK-II operated with half of ID PMTs due to the accident that occurred during the detector maintenance work after SK-I. Except for that phase, SK has been operating with 40 % photo coverage ID PMTs. New front-end electronics [4] and data acquisition system were introduced in 2008 and they enable to tag faint 2.2 MeV gamma ray signals from the neutron captures on hydrogen. Thanks to this neutron tagging technique, about 50 % atmospheric neutrino background reduction for proton decay signal was achieved by requiring no tagged neutrons, because atmospheric neutrino interactions are often accompanied by neutrons. The data from April 1996 to March 2015 are used for the last published results for $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ modes [5].

Event topology and its kinematic information is obtained through the event reconstruction algorithm [7] with recored ID PMT timing and charge values. They are reconstructed in the order of charged particle production vertex, number of Cherenkov

Table 1: Summary of the SK data taking period.

	Livetime (days)	ID Photo coverage (%)	Note
SK-I	1489.2	40	
SK-II	798.6	19	Half number of ID PMTs
SK-III	518.1	40	
SK-IV	3244.4	40	New electronics and DAQ systems

rings, particle type and momentum. At first, the vertex position is reconstructed using mainly PMT timing information. Then, the number of Cherenkov rings projected on the detector wall is counted. For each Cherenkov ring, particle type is identified as a showering particle (e^\pm, γ) or non-showering particle (μ^\pm, π^\pm) with its Cherenkov ring pattern. Particle mis-identification probability is less than 1 % level for 1 GeV single ring events and it is well demonstrated with atmospheric neutrino data and MC. At last, each particle momentum is estimated from the total charge associated with each ring. Momentum resolution is estimated to be about 3 % for 1 GeV single ring event and energy scale uncertainty is also estimated to be about 3 % using cosmic-ray muons, their Michel electrons and neutral pion mass spectrum in atmospheric neutrino events. Neutrons emitted from primary events thermalize in water and are eventually captured by a hydrogen or oxygen nucleus. Thanks to the electronics upgrade, 2.2 MeV gamma rays emitted from deuteron nucleus excited state can be identified in the SK-IV phase data. The true neutron tagging efficiency is about 25 % with less than 2 % mis-tagging probability.

3 Enlarging the Fiducial Mass

In the conventional analysis [5], the defined fiducial mass region is located more than 2 m from the ID wall and corresponds to 22.5 kton of water. This exposure is the world largest for proton decay search but its sensitivity is still limited by statistics. To further increase the detector exposure, following studies associated with data quality and reconstruction performance have been conducted to enlarge the fiducial mass region;

- A. Non-neutrino background (external background contamination) estimation.
- B. Event reconstruction improvement about particle identification.

An event scanning work has been conducted for the events which have vertex more than 50 cm from the ID wall to estimate non-neutrino external background contamination level near the ID wall region. Nearer to the ID wall (outside of the detector), more external background events such as cosmic-ray muons and dummy events induced by PMT flashing have been found. Several new event selection cuts have been developed to reject mainly cosmic-ray muons on top of the existing algorithms [8], and thanks to new cuts, cosmic-ray muons could be reduced by about 70 %. Finally, we have concluded to enlarge fiducial mass region up to 100 cm to the ID wall to keep external background contamination rate within 1 % to the total number of events.

Shower type or non-shower type ring is identified by comparing the expected ID PMT charge distribution in each particle type assumption with the observed charge distribution. For events occurring in the enlarged region, because of their event topologies and the detector geometry, the number of ID PMT hits tends to be fewer than in the conventional region. Less ID PMT hits makes the event reconstruction, especially particle identification, more difficult. Since in this situation, each ID PMT hit information becomes more important, the expected charge tables used in the calculation have been retuned with the detector simulation to improve the performance. Thanks to the revised expected charge tables and particle identification performance improvement, proton decay signal selection efficiency has been improved by about 20 %.

We have enlarged the fiducial mass of the Super-Kamiokande detector by 20 % (22.5 kton to 27.2 kton) and added 25 % more exposure by livetime update since the last paper [5], resulting in 1.5 times larger statistics (306 kton·years to 450 kton·years).

4 $p \rightarrow e^+ \pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+ \pi^0$ Mode Searches

Following event selection criteria are applied to signal MC, atmospheric neutrino MC and data.

Cut-1 Events must satisfy all fully contained event selection criteria with the vertex position within the fiducial mass region.

Cut-2 There must be 2 or 3 reconstructed Cherenkov rings.

Cut-3 All rings must be reconstructed as a shower-like ring for $p \rightarrow e^+ \pi^0$ and one ring must be a non shower-like ring for $p \rightarrow \mu^+ \pi^0$.

Cut-4 There must be no tagged Michel electrons for $p \rightarrow e^+ \pi^0$ and one for $p \rightarrow \mu^+ \pi^0$.

Cut-5 Reconstructed π^0 mass must be $85 < M_{\pi^0} < 185$ MeV/c².

Cut-6 Reconstructed total mass must be $800 < M_{tot} < 1050$ MeV/c².

Cut-7 Reconstructed total momentum must be $P_{tot} < 250$ MeV/c.

Cut-8 There must be no tagged neutrons for SK-IV data.

The signal efficiencies and the expected number of atmospheric neutrino background events for both the conventional region and the enlarged region are estimated by applying the same selection cuts. The signal region is further divided into the lower total momentum region ($P_{tot} < 100$ MeV/c) and the higher total momentum region ($100 \leq P_{tot} < 250$ MeV/c) same as in the last paper [5]. The SKI-IV livetime averaged signal efficiencies, the total expected number of backgrounds and the number of data candidates are summarized in the Table 2. The signal efficiencies in the enlarged region are lower than those in the conventional region because of fewer ID PMT hits and escaping particles from the ID to outside. The total mass v.s. total momentum distributions are shown in Figures 1,2. In the lower P_{tot} signal regions, most free proton decay events are reconstructed and almost background free. The search sensitivity has been estimated with the conventional fiducial mass (22.5 kton)

performances and the larger fiducial mass (27.2 kton) performances. Then, it is confirmed that enlarging fiducial mass increases the proton decay search sensitivity by about 12 %.

Table 2: Summary of $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ mode search performances and results. "Inclusive" column corresponds to 27.2 kton larger fiducial mass performances and results.

$p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$				
	Signal Region	Conventional (22.5 kton)	Enlarged (4.7 kton)	Inclusive (27.2 kton)
Signal Efficiency	Lower P_{tot}	19.6%	10.3%	18.1%
	Higher P_{tot}	20.3%	15.5%	19.5%
The expected number of atmospheric ν backgrounds	Lower P_{tot}	0.01	0.01	0.02
	Higher P_{tot}	0.48	0.09	0.57
Data Candidates	Lower P_{tot}	0	0	0
	Higher P_{tot}	0	0	0

$p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$				
	Signal Region	Conventional (22.5 kton)	Enlarged (4.7 kton)	Inclusive (27.2 kton)
Signal Efficiency	Lower P_{tot}	18.5%	11.7%	17.4%
	Higher P_{tot}	17.8%	13.5%	17.1%
The expected number of atmospheric ν backgrounds	Lower P_{tot}	0.04	0.01	0.05
	Higher P_{tot}	0.70	0.19	0.89
Data Candidates	Lower P_{tot}	0	0	0
	Higher P_{tot}	1	0	1

For the $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ mode, there are no candidates in the signal region while for the $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ mode, there is one event in the signal region and it is the same event reported in the last paper [5]. The number of data candidates is not significant compared to the total (lower and higher P_{tot}) expected number of backgrounds ($p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$: 0.59, $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$: 0.94) in the enlarged fiducial mass. Finally, the lower limits on the partial lifetime for both modes are calculated, $\tau_{p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0} > 2.4 \times 10^{34}$ years and $\tau_{p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0} > 1.6 \times 10^{34}$ years at 90 % confidence level. They are 1.5 to 2.0 times longer lifetime limits than those reported in the last paper [5] and the world most stringent limits.

5 Other Decay Mode Search Results

In the previous sections, $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ mode results are covered, and in this section, other decay mode search results are described. It should be noted that all results in this section are based on the 22.5 kton conventional fiducial mass analysis and not using all the Super-Kamiokande data, so there is room for statistical improvement.

In SUSY GUT models [9], the $p \rightarrow \bar{\nu}K^+$ can have a high branching ratio through dimension five operators. In a water Cherenkov detector, a charged Kaon from the proton decay is below the Cherenkov threshold and does not emit Cherenkov photons. It is expected to stop inside the water and decay mainly via $K^+ \rightarrow \nu\mu^+$ (leptonic

Figure 1: Reconstructed total mass v.s. total momentum distributions for $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ after all the cuts except the cuts on these variables. The top plots correspond to the conventional region and the bottom plots correspond to the enlarged region. The left panels show the signal MC events, where light colors are free protons and dark colors are bound protons. The middle panels show 2000 years equivalent atmospheric neutrino MC events. The right panels show all the data results from SK-I to SK-IV. The black box is signal region. For the middle panels, the dot size is enlarged in the signal box.

Figure 2: Reconstructed total mass v.s. total momentum distributions for $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ after all the cuts except the cuts on these variables. The top plots correspond to the conventional region and the bottom plots correspond to the enlarged region. The left panels show the signal MC events, where light colors are free protons and dark colors are bound protons. The middle panels show 2000 years equivalent atmospheric neutrino MC events. The right panels show all the data results from SK-I to SK-IV. The black box is signal region. For the middle and right panels, the dot size is enlarged in the signal box.

decay channel: $\text{Br} \sim 60\%$) or $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^0$ (hadronic decay channel: $\text{Br} \sim 20\%$) with a lifetime of ~ 12 nsec. Following three different search methods are applied to cover these channels.

- a. Tag a de-excitation gamma ray (typically 6.3 MeV) from remaining ^{15}N nucleus after a proton decays in an ^{16}O nucleus, a 236 MeV/c momentum muon from Kaon decay and a Michel electron from muon decay. The signal efficiency is about 9 %.
- b. Fit muon momentum distribution of data with signal and atmospheric neutrino background MC and search for a signal bump around 236 MeV/c. The signal efficiency is about 35 %.
- c. Search for a $\pi^+\pi^0$ back-to-back signal, with each momentum of 205 MeV/c. The signal efficiency is about 9 %.

The methods a. and b. focus on the leptonic decay channel and c. on the hadronic decay channel. With the Super-Kamiokande data until February 2018 (365 kton-years), no significant data excess nor signal bump have been observed. The lifetime limit for this decay mode is obtained: $\tau_{p \rightarrow \nu K^+} > 8.2 \times 10^{33}$ years. Detailed descriptions about this decay mode search can be found in [10].

So far, no significant nucleon decay signal have been confirmed in Super-Kamiokande. The obtained nucleon decay lifetime limits are summarized in Figure 3 including other decay modes not mentioned above [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16].

Figure 3: Summary of nucleon decay lifetime limits obtained by Super-Kamiokande.

6 Summary

We have searched for proton decay via $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ and $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$ with the Super-Kamiokande enlarged fiducial mass data until May 2018, 450 kton-years exposure in total. No candidate have been found for the $p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0$ mode and one candidate remains for the $p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0$. We set lower limits on the partial lifetime for each of these modes: $\tau_{p \rightarrow e^+\pi^0} > 2.4 \times 10^{34}$ years and $\tau_{p \rightarrow \mu^+\pi^0} > 1.6 \times 10^{34}$ years at 90 % confidence level. They are more than 1.5 times longer than those reported in the last paper [5]. No evidence for nucleon decay has been confirmed including the other decay modes but the world stringent limits are obtained for almost all of them by Super-Kamiokande and there is still room for increasing the data statistics by adding livetime and enlarging the fiducial mass for them.

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